

Bifunctional organometallic catalysts for selective hydration of nitriles to amides

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In this report, we highlight our recent contributions towards the development of bifunctional catalysts for selective hydration of nitriles to amides.

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Introduction

The wide and varied use of amides in industry, pharmaceuticals and synthetic chemistry makes the development of atom-economical and sustainable synthetic methods for functionalized amides an important objective in organometallic chemistry¹. Acrylic monomers are valuable precursors for polyacrylamides². However, conventional protocols to access amides suffer from several drawbacks. Nitrile hydration is a highly desired atom economic pathway (Scheme 1)³ that avoids the generation of toxic waste associated with typical amide synthesis techniques such as coupling of activated carboxylic derivatives with amines, Schmidt reaction, Staudinger-Vilarrasa reaction and Beckmann rearrangements⁴. Traditional nitrile hydration methods using acid or base catalysis cause over-hydrolysis to the acid products and tolerate only a limited number of functional groups⁵.

Scheme 1. Nitrile hydration reaction.

Nitrile hydratases (NHases), a class of enzymes containing low-spin non-heme iron(III) or non-corrin cobalt(III) active sites hydrates nitriles to amides (Scheme 2)⁶. In absence of a convenient molecular catalyst, industrial-scale productions of various amide-based pharmaceutical drugs are carried out via biocatalysis using these metalloenzymes. However, high isolation cost and substrate specificity severely restrict their

Scheme 2. Active site and catalytic reaction of NHases.

wider applications.

Several homogeneous and heterogeneous organometallic catalysts containing Co, Ni, Cu, Mo, Ru, Rh, Pd, Ag, Os, Ir, Pt, Au have been reported⁷. Many of these catalysts are designed following *bifunctional* approach where a cooperative combination of Lewis acidic metal and basic (Brønsted) ligand site activates a small molecule⁸. Oshiki and co-workers reported *cis*-Ru(acac)₂(Ph₂Ppy)₂ catalyst where the pyridyl unit of the ligand promotes the nitrile hydration activity⁹. Cadeirno group has made remarkable progress using homogeneous Ru, Rh and Os catalysts containing pyridyl-phosphines, aminoaryl-phosphines, thiazolyl-phosphines, 1,3,5-triaza-7-phosphaadamantane (PTA) and amino-phosphines¹⁰. In this report, we describe our recent efforts on bifunctional nitrile hydration reactions and the underlying mechanistic insights.

Our group reported a Rh^I naphthyridine (NP)

functionalized N-heterocyclic carbene (NHC) complex **1** where the free nitrogens of the NP unit were utilized for water activation exploiting hydrogen-bonding interactions¹¹. Complex **1** is a highly efficient catalyst in the transformation of organonitriles to the corresponding primary amides at room temperature (Scheme 3). A catalyst tube was charged with 0.005 mmol isopropanol solution of **1**, organonitrile (1 mmol), ^tBuOK (0.1 mmol), water (1 mL), and the resulting solution was stirred at room temperature. The amide product was purified by column chromatography using petroleum ether/ethyl acetate as eluent. No traces of over hydrated acids or esters were detected throughout the entire course of the reaction. The reaction was found to be accelerated in alcoholic solvents viz. methanol, ethanol and isopropanol when compared to other polar solvents such as dimethyl acetamide or dimethyl sulfoxide. An increase in catalyst loading led to only marginal improvement in yields for poorly reacting sterically demanding nitriles. Apart from an array of nitrile substrates (21 entries), catalyst **1** was also employed for the synthesis of acrylamide, which is precursor material for the industrially important polyacrylamide. By tuning the catalyst loading and the reaction time, a turnover frequency up to 20000 could be achieved.

Scheme 3. ORTEP diagram (50% probability thermal ellipsoids) of **1** with important atoms labeled. **1** was evaluated as a nitrile hydration catalyst. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 11. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society.

In order to verify the hypothesis that a pendant basic group is vital for nitrile hydration, [Rh(COD)(κ-C₂-Me₂-NHC)Br] (Me₂-NHC = 1,3-dimethylimidazol-2-ylidene) complex, that is devoid of the NP group, was synthesized. Under optimized reaction conditions, it gave only 30% benzamide along with over hydrated products. This observation suggests a ligand assisted nitrile hydration mechanism¹².

DFT calculations based on B3LYP level of theory were undertaken considering acetonitrile as a model substrate. It is important for both water and nitrile to bind at the metal. The pyridyl nitrogen polarizes a metal-coordinated water through hydrogen bond interactions and nucleophilic water attack is favored for a metal-bound nitrile. Accordingly, a nitrile bound intermediate **A** was computed which is formed upon removal of a bromide from **1** in the presence of catalytic amount of base. Intermediate **B** reveals crucial double hydrogen bonded water adduct to two NP nitrogens (Scheme 4)¹². These interactions compensate for the entropic loss by bringing a water molecule from the bulk to the vicinity of the metal center. The water then coordinates to the metal and makes a hydrogen bond interaction with NP nitrogen as well (N-H = 1.796 Å) to form intermediate **C**.

These secondary interactions help in orienting the oxygen lone pair of water for a nucleophilic attack to the nitrile through a relevant **TS-CD** to form the intermediate **D**. The imido form in **D** tautomerizes to the amido form **E**. In the next step, there are two possibilities for reaching to amide coordinated intermediate **G**; (i) Direct proton transfer from naphthyridine nitrogen to amido nitrogen, (ii) Proton transfer from naphthyridine nitrogen to amido oxygen generating intermediate **F** followed by a tautomerization. The release of the amide product and subsequent coordination of a substrate molecule closes the catalytic cycle. Thus, DFT calculations support a hydroxide attack to metal-coordinated water that is promoted by the ligand. The activation of water by cooperative actions of the metal and the ligand illustrates a 'bifunctional water activation' mechanism.

It is now widely recognized that a heteroatom present in the ligand backbone accelerates nitrile hydration. However, catalysts containing a free basic group may impose several problems leading to its deactivation. Protic impurities may diminish its catalytic activity. The prospect of a stable dimer formation is detrimental for catalytic activity. Bulky ancillary ligands such as phosphines or NHCs are needed in the ligand

Scheme 4. DFT calculated mechanism for nitrile hydration by **1**.

scaffold which imposes a significant synthetic challenge. To circumvent these limitations, we proposed the use of hemilabile proton responsive unit on the catalyst for water activation¹³. The basic premise is that a hemilabile group would open up under the reaction conditions to allow a water molecule to the metal center and would further activate the same water molecule by secondary interactions. Employment of a hemilabile group might also increase the selectivity and overall turnover values¹⁴.

We have recently reported hemilability driven nitrile hydration by a functionalized NHC based Ni^{II} catalyst without requiring any additives or base¹⁵. A pyridyl and hydroxy functionalized NHC ligated Ni^{II} complex **2** was synthesized. The molecular structure of **2** showed two NHC bound ligands in a *cis* position and the other two coordination sites are bound

to the pyridine ring (Scheme 5). A linkage isomer **2'** was obtained by crystallization from a concentrated solution of complex **2** in CH₃CN/CH₃OH (1:1) mixture layered with Et₂O at -20°C. In this isomer **2'**, the hydroxyl groups are ligated to the metal center in lieu of the pyridines. Isolation of two linkage isomers under different crystallization conditions indicated hemilabile behavior of the complex.

Catalytic activity of **2** was examined for the hydration of benzonitrile with 2 mol% catalyst loading in H₂O/PrOH (1:3 v/v) at 70°C and showed 91% conversion after 6 h. A range of organonitriles (aromatic and aliphatic) was employed as substrates and they showed excellent conversions under these optimized conditions (18 entries).

Hydration of cyanohydrins is inherently difficult as it rapidly decomposes in solution to produce ketones and HCN

Scheme 5. Structure of **2** and its linkage isomer **2'**. **2** was evaluated as a nitrile hydration catalyst.

which poison the metal catalyst¹⁶. This problem can be overcome by performing the reaction in a neutral condition¹⁷. Since catalyst **2** could hydrate range of nitriles under base-free conditions, it inspired us to examine its effectiveness for the catalytic hydration of cyanohydrins. Gratifyingly, up to 70% yields were obtained for typical cyanohydrins such as 4-chloromandelonitrile in presence of slightly increased 10 mol% catalyst loading (Scheme 6). Bioactive amides such

as pyrazinamide (commercially sold as Rifater®)¹⁸, 2-(2-oxopyrrolidin-1-yl)acetamide, also commonly known as Piracetam¹⁹ and nicotinamide²⁰ were synthesized using **2** as a catalyst from their nitrile precursors. Catalyst **2** was also used for the synthesis of Rufinamide, an antiepileptic drug²¹. The nitrile precursor was prepared from 2-(bromomethyl)-1,3-difluorobenzene and 2-chloroacrylonitrile and subsequent hydration afforded Rufinamide which was characterized by

Scheme 6. Hydration of cyanohydrins and synthesis of bio-active amides. X-Ray structure of Rufinamide is provided inset.

X-ray crystallography and NMR spectroscopy. Energy dispersive X-ray analysis revealed no Ni incorporation in the product.

Several control experiments were carried out to delve into the mechanistic possibilities. Three very similar compounds **3**, **4** and **5** were synthesized (Scheme 7). Complex **3**, which was devoid of a pyridyl group showed extremely poor conversions whereas **4** which lacks the hydroxy group showed slightly lower conversions when compared to **2**. A third compound **5** was also synthesized that was devoid of both the pyridyl and hydroxy functionalities and showed the poorest activity amongst all. It is thus evident that the water activating pyridyl group and the hydroxy appendage on the ligand scaffold in the parent catalyst **2** contributed to its increased hydration activity.

We assumed that the catalytic activity involves the decoordination of the hemilabile pyridyl unit from the metal center to activate water through secondary interactions. When

catalyst **4** and TfOH 1:2 (*m/m*) mixture in CH₃CN/H₂O was titrated against standard 0.01 M NaOH solution at room temperature, no equivalence point could be reached. Whereas a sigmoidal curve was obtained when the same mixture was heated at 70°C for 1 h followed by titration against standard NaOH solution and the pK_a value of 2.51 was estimated. Again when an 1:1 (*m/m*) mixture of free imidazolium precursor of **4** and TfOH in acetonitrile/water mixture was titrated at room temperature against a standard NaOH solution, a pK_a of 2.99 was obtained. This observation is in accordance with the proposal that the metal-bound pyridine ring is not available for protonation at room temperature but at elevated temperature becomes unbound and protonated in an acidic medium.

Further, kinetic experiments were performed. 4-Nitrobenzonitrile was taken as a model substrate to check the effect of temperature on the reaction rate of **2** (Fig. 1). The activation parameters were determined from ln (*k*/T) ver-

Scheme 7. Control catalysts **3**, **4** and **5** (top). Titration curves obtained by titrating (a) 1:2 (*m/m*) of **4** and TfOH in acetonitrile/water 3:1 (*v/v*) at 70°C for 1 h against 0.01 M NaOH; (b) 1:1 (*m/m*) of imidazolium precursor of **4** and TfOH in CH₃CN/H₂O 3:1 (*v/v*) against 0.01 M NaOH. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 15. Copyright 2017, John Wiley and Sons.

sus $1/T$ plot and the estimated entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) was calculated to be $-33.39 \pm 0.56 \text{ Kcal mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. An organized and associative transition state involving water, nitrile

and catalyst is indicated by experimentally determined highly negative ΔS^\ddagger value. The relative rates ($\log(k_X/k_H)$) were plotted against the substituent constant (σ) yielding a fairly good

Fig. 1. Arrhenius plot for hydration of 4-nitrobenzonitrile catalyzed by **2** over 333–353 K and Hammett plot for competitive hydration of benzonitrile and *p*-substituted derivatives catalyzed by **2** at 343 K. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 15. Copyright 2017, John Wiley and Sons.

Scheme 8. Proposed mechanism for nitrile hydration by **2** (for clarity, benzimidazole is replaced with imidazole).

linear relationship. Hammett plot having positive slope ($\rho = +2.47 \pm 0.19$) implies that the reaction is favored in presence of electron withdrawing substituents. The negative charge is generated at α -carbon atom nearby to the phenyl ring during the rate determining step. As linearity in $\log(k_X/k_H)$ vs σ^- plot could not be achieved, it can be concluded that the negative charge generated at α -carbon in the transition state should be partial. Thus, a concerted nucleophilic water attack to the metal-bound nitrile is more likely than a hydroxide attack under neutral base-free conditions²². This was further conform by Kinetic Isotope Effect (KIE) studies²³.

Based on these studies, a tentative mechanism was proposed where the pyridyl unit *trans* to the NHC decoordinates and allows a water molecule to bind the metal (Scheme 8). The pyridyl nitrogen polarizes and promotes a water attack to the nitrile in a concerted pathway and forms an iminol intermediate followed by a rapid tautomerization to a metal-amide intermediate.

An alternative route involving water proton abstraction by the pyridyl nitrogen with a concurrent hydroxide attack to the nitrile carbon was discarded because no significant Ki-

netic Isotope Effect was observed with D_2O . Moreover, Hammett plots suggested that complete charge transfer is unlikely during the rate determining step. pK_a studies reveal that the pyridyl nitrogen is not basic enough to abstract a proton from a water molecule under neutral conditions²⁴. This work shows that a hemilabile basic ligand is an effective strategy to develop selective nitrile hydration catalyst involving even a 3d-metal under base/additive free conditions.

Conclusions

In this report, we demonstrate the efficacies of bifunctional catalysts for selective nitrile hydration to amides. Pyridyl-type nitrogen in the vicinity of the metal center accelerates nitrile hydration by promoting nucleophilic water attack to a metal-bound nitrile via secondary interactions. In neutral medium, water attacks the nitrile whereas a hydroxide is the nucleophile under basic conditions. Use of hemilabile ligands allows better catalyst design leading to higher efficiency and selectivity. These studies offer viable options for synthetic nitrile hydration catalyst under homogeneous conditions.

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